

Identification of Symptoms in Eye Images to Predict the disease of Diabetic Retinopathy by Using A3 –Layered Convolution Neural Network

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ABSTRACT: One of the leading causes of loss of sight and eye disease in working era of cultivated globe is Diabetic Retinopathy. The proposal is an effort for discovering a programmed technique to identify Diabetic Retinopathy in the initial stage. Here, we are exercising supervised learning methods [11] for classifying a given set of images into 2 classes. To identify the retinopathy in humans who are undergoing diabetes since long time, we used various image processing techniques and filters to improve the features. A good number of pre-trained models are available to perform classification of an input image with Convolution Neural Networks (CNN). This proposal is to create a model to help the eye affected people in listing the of the problem in detail and the expected output provides them a clear idea about the symptoms of Diabetic Retinopathy. This can be beneficial for the people who are bothered about Diabetic Retinopathy happening. During the process, Data mining will help to retrieve the required information from huge amounts of datasets accumulated. A flask model is build using available datasets of patients to predict Diabetic Retinopathy.

Keywords: Diabetic Retinopathy, CNN, Classification, Augmentation.

1. Introduction

Diabetic Retinopathy is an eye disorder affected owing in injury of blood vessels in Retina. It is a Visual symptom of diabetes. Few indications of Diabetic Retinopathy may incorporate Sudden loss of Vision, Patchy or Blurry Vision, Floating shapes in vision, Dark Spots, Double Vision, Redness in Eye, Leakage of Blood Vessels, Pain in eyes, Loss of vision at the corners of the eyes, Retina Swelling. Diabetes complications cause DR, which eventually leads to blindness. According to WHO data, 347 million people worldwide suffer from diabetes, with 40 – 45 percent of them having Diabetic Retinopathy at some stage.

The prevailing approach involves eye screening for detecting DR done manually at trained clinicians by scrutinizing digital pictures, which frequently scores in miscommunication and postponed outcomes, which ultimately results in suspended treatment. The following are some of the current scenario's flaws: (a) desires extreme investment set – up costs, (b) complications in reaching all patients who needs to be screened, (c) a prerequisite to provide systematic training for the grader, (d) camera systems may have to rotate around practises, potentially limiting accessibility of the amenity.

Our goal is to provide an automated, appropriate, and advanced approach that uses Image Processing and Pattern Recognition [15] to detect Diabetic Retinopathy at an initial stage and minimise retina damage. This proposal investigates the present practices and applications for Diabetic Retinopathy diagnosis and recognition techniques. This detection approach includes:

- an automated acquisition
- assessment and
- image

Our approach has four major components, namely;

- (a) An acquisition of image,
- (b) The processing of image,
- (c) The extraction of feature, and
- (d) The several Classification Machine Learning Techniques.

Convolutional Neural Network is a division of Deep Neural Networks, usually applied to explore visual or photographic metaphors (images). CNN accepts image as an input, assign weights and biases, and will differentiate one from the other. As the essence of the information exploration process, CNN is a brand. Different measures are engaged in extracting knowledge from the datasets.

A Variety of data mining techniques like Clustering, Classification, Prediction, Association Rule Mining, and many more, employed with set of pre-classified samples to build a model that can perform classification on huge records of the population. This approach typically uses the classification Decision Tree —based Classification [4] Algorithm. To create the model, a training set is used, and the classifier classifies the data items into suitable classes. A test set is applied to authenticate the proposed prototype.

2. Literature Survey

Convolutional Neural Network is a division of Deep Neural Networks, usually applied to explore visual or photographic metaphors (images). CNN accepts image as an input, assign weights and biases, and will differentiate one from the other. As the essence of the information exploration process, CNN is a brand. Different measures are engaged in extracting knowledge from the datasets.

Basically, there are 2 stages of Diabetic Retinopathy. They are 1) Diabetic Retinopathy (DR) 2) No Diabetic Retinopathy (NDR). DR is further classified into Background Retinopathy and Degree of Referable Retinopathy. Background Retinopathy represents Stage 1 which indicates the patients must visit for screening once in every 12 months. Degree of Referable Retinopathy represents Stage 2 or Stage 3 which

Fig 1: Difference in Normal Eye and Diabetic Retinopathy Eye

Fig 2: Affected areas in an eye for a Diabetic Retinopathy Patient

indicates the patients should have very frequent tests and talks with the specialist about possible treatments. Stage 1, Stage 2, and Stage 3 cannot be cured but, vision can be improved through Laser treatments.

Fig 1 shows the variation in blood vessels among normal eye and retinopathy affected eye, where it evidently reveals the leakage of fluid from the blood vessels of an eye into the retina. Such outflow indicates the symptoms of Diabetic Retinopathy. Fig 2 shows the sections affected in an eye and Fig 3 shows few symptoms for a

Diabetic patient. As per recent research made by WHO, nearly 5% of total blindness cases are caused due to diabetes.

People suffering from Vision Threatening Diabetic Retinopathy will rise from 7.7 million in 2014 to 11 million in 2030 and 14.5 million till 2050 [7], expanding research for the future. By using the approach of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) Image Analysis Convolution Layer [6], Flatten Layer, Dense Layer etc., for early recognition of Diabetic Retinopathy.

Fig 3: Few Symptoms of Diabetic Retinopathy

While in studying embryonic version of medical photos, deep neural networks [13] are exploring, the majority of surveys restrict their methodology to a single supervised transfer learning [11], which typically relies heavily on a large-scale interpreted training dataset. It can be achieved using a Deep Convolution Neural Network architecture that is skilled with data of binary image sets to comprehend image representations with less supervision. Few scholars assessed, the trained image representations using a multiclass diabetic retinopathy fundus image [3] dataset which is available publicly. The problem can be cracked employing Deep CNN which significantly involves a reduced amount of supervision for training.

While opting the algorithm that delivers an accurate prediction, we have turned through bunch of algorithms which offered the results abruptly accurate and from them we designated merely one procedure for the prediction problem and that is neural networks. Neural networks [13] give the output based on the independent variables accurately. The eccentricity of this problem is, amassing the particulars of the person with diabetic retinopathy warning signs in real time and working with the prediction at the same time. As a consequence, we designed a user interface for the individuals experiencing symptoms who will be accessing the diabetic retinopathy prediction.

There are several methods for determining the accuracy of a Convolutional Neural Network. Typically, we employ Root Mean Squared Error. We train convolutional neural network by adding or removing the features from dataset and then compare the results to see which one has the lowest Root Mean Square Error. The one with lowest Root MSE is regarded as the best one. Initially, we got a lot of bad accuracies because we tried lot of algorithms to find the most accurate algorithm. Finally, after all of that, we attempted the finest appropriate algorithm which affords the accurate prediction, which is Convolutional Neural Network, and thus developed it to use as a real time prediction problem for the prediction of Diabetic Retinopathy.

Diabetic Retinopathy comes in a variety of forms, according to the review of the literature. A few examples include (a) Diabetic Macular Edema, (b) Glaucoma, (c) Cataracts [7]. The Macula is a chunk of the retina, which is vital for seeing faces, driving, and reading. Diabetic Macula Edema, a type of swelling in the macula caused by diabetes. This syndrome can gradually ruin the intense sight in this portion of the eye, resulting in partial eyesight loss or impaired vision. Macular Edema typically appears in individuals who previously have Diabetic Retinopathy.

Glaucoma, a group of eye ailments that can harm the optical nerve, the bunch of nerves that connect the eye to the brain. Diabetes amplifies the risk of glaucoma, which lead to vision deficiency and loss of sight if not cured in the early hours. The lenses within our eye are evident structures that assist in providing intense vision, but they have a tendency to turn out to be cloudy as we grow older. Individuals with diabetes are further expected to build milky lenses, termed Cataracts [7]. Folks with diabetes can acquire Cataracts [7] at a younger period than people deprived of diabetes. Scientists believe that extreme glucose readings trigger accumulations to form Cataracts [7] in the crystalline lens of the eyes.

Diabetic Retinopathy is a critical civic health crisis that weakens the quality of life, and current medications are constrained to invasive choices such as photocoagulation and intraocular vaccinations. Because of the nature of Retinopathy and the inability to isolate the retinal tissue from living patients, we heavily rely on animal models and tissue cultures to diagnose early changes to combat this disease. The key factor in case of Diabetic Reti-

nopathy is to identify particular spots and traces of oxidative pressure, to inhibit the onset and progression of the ocular complications of the diabetes. An interpretation of the organic changes and molecular actions that control growth – factor signalling in diabetes and knowledge of medications that selectively aim for oxidative pressure mediated protein variation can lead to new and effective therapies.

3. Problem Definition:

The primary goal of diagnosing and treating Diabetic Retinopathy is to (a) thwart, (b) delay, (c) reversal vision loss, thus sustaining or enhancing eyesight-related condition of life. Digital pigment retinal images [10] are becoming progressively more vital in ophthalmology for the diagnosis of diabetic retinopathy. Image pre-processing techniques are used in computer-based retinal image analysis systems to accelerate and enhance diagnosis. Manual image evaluation can be upgraded, and the challenge of detecting diabetic retinopathy in the later phase for optimal therapy can be solved.

This challenge can be deciphered using the Architecture of Deep Convolution Neural Network that will be trained with merely binary vision pair evidence to learn image representations with less supervision. Some researchers tested the well - read image descriptions on a task of subject-based medical image retrieval using a publicly available multiclass diabetic retinopathy fundus image [3] dataset.

Pre-processing is used competently in the field of medicine to diagnose diseases. It's too difficult to derive relevant data from the resulting image's amalgamation. Thus, semi-supervised [11] learning is very useful for segmentation, and the end result can be finely adjusted using Deep Learning Neural Network. Although Deep Neural Networks [13] have been studied for understanding hidden illustrations of medical images, most surveys regulate their line to Single Supervised Transfer Learning [11] or supervised convolution neural network, which is typically trained using a large-scale annotated dataset.

We will follow the following process for image recognition [15] for the above discussion. In step 1, we will define and classify the Diabetic Retinopathy. Step 2 identifies the diagnostic criteria for different categories. Step 3 lists the signs and symptoms of Diabetic Retinopathy. Step 4 states why signs and symptoms occur. Step 5, the last one describes the role of genetic and environment factors in the prevention and management of Diabetic Retinopathy.

Few limitations exist in our projected scheme which are mentioned as (a) The proposed project can predict only 76% accuracy of the image, (b) The proposed system can authenticate only one eye at a given time, (c) The dataset comprises of great figure of images of several classes, and it is imbalanced, (d) The dataset associated with this theme is noisy and entails multiple pre-processing stepladders to acquire all images to a customary format for training a model.

4. Proposed System:

The framework we suggested is a Convolution layer [6], MaxPooling [2] [5], Reflected Linear Unit (ReLU) [16] 3-layered architecture as preliminary, intermediate, and final layers, respectively. CNN Architecture has (1) Input, holds the pixel values of the images given as Input, (2) Convolutionary Layer [6], determines the desired output, (3) ReLU layer [16], performs the wise activation function of the element, (4) MaxPooling [2] layer [5], reduces the height or width size or volume.

Figure 4 represents the information of process how the model works and a system for detection of various stages of Diabetic Retinopathy. Initially, the retina image is given as an input to the proposed system, then the pre - processing of the given image is accomplished. Further, this model will obtain the features of the image and will assess these features with the normal picture based on the distinctions in the image.

The Growth of the Algorithm:

Deep learning is a means of training a Neural Network [13], which is a significant mathematical function with billions of parameters to execute a specific task. The function calculates the severity of Diabetic Retinopathy based on the amounts of the pixels in the given image [3].

Fig 4: Content Diagram of Diabetic Retinopathy.

Designing or training this task necessitates a larger set of pictures for which the severity of Diabetic Retinopathy is already well-known and let us call this large collection of images used for creating or training as “Training Set”.

Initially, the retina image is given as input to the proposed system. This projected system computes the severity of Diabetic Retinopathy from the given pixels intensity in the fundus image [3]. To train our system lots of retina images with diagnosed Diabetic Retinopathy are required. Primarily, the parameter values of neural network [13] are haphazard. Then, the severity of Diabetic Retinopathy is associated to that known from the training set for each picture. The task parameter values are revised during this process to decline the inaccuracy in the image.

The mentioned function is repetitive for all the appropriate ‘n’ images in the teaching set, and by this the function understands how to calculate the intensity of Diabetic Retinopathy of the new images. This method uses a Coevolutionary Neural Network that determines a feature that later merges the nearby pixels into local components into global components. May be this system cannot identify wounds like Haemorrhages or Micro Aneurysms but can recognize using local elements. Inception v-3 [12], the architecture of the neural network proposed by Szeged et al [8], is used here.

As per the protocol, data pre-processing needs to be done. Distributed Stochastic Gradient Descent, an optimization algorithm, by Dean et al [14] is used to train the weights of the network. To fasten the training and performance, both Batch Normalization and pre – initialization of weights is performed for objects classification [4] in ImageNet dataset [6] [15] [16] is used.

A network is qualified to create numerous binary prophecies whether the image was (i) Mild or Inferior Diabetic Retinopathy, (ii) Acute or inferior Diabetic Retinopathy, (iii) Imputable Diabetic Macular Edema, or (iv) Absolutely Gradable [1]. Imputable Diabetic Retinopathy was characterized as any aura that accomplished either criteria (i), criteria (iii) or both. The vicinity beneath the Receiver Operating Curve (AUC) spawned by scheming Sensitivity [9] versus 1-Specificity was used to assess the preferred algorithm’s performance. Since the system in this research had a huge quantity of parameters approximately 22 million, an early stopping criterion was used to cease training beforehand convergence or technically breaks training when zenith AUC was reached on a distinct tuning set.

The dataset was divided into 2 parts. They are (1) Training (2) Tuning. The former uses 80% of the data to augment the weights of the network and latter uses 20% of the data to augment hyper – parameters namely Early Training Stoppage, Image pre – processing options. An ensemble of 10 networks were focused on the consistent data and the last expectation was calculated by a direct or straight path across the estimations of the group.

The model was designed through a series of steps including pre – processing, training, and augmentation [16]. The dataset includes patients’ images of various ethnicities, mature groupings, and exceptionally various amounts of illumination in the main photo. This has an effect on the pixel concentration values in the images, causing avoidable variation that is irrelevant to the classification stages [4].

To counteract this, the OpenCV (<http://opencv.org/>) package was implemented to perform color [10] normalization on the images. The images were also high-level resolution, requiring a substantial amount of memorial size [14]. The dataset was reconstructed to 512x512 pixels, which preserved the convoluted features we intended to recognize while shrinking the dataset to a memorial extent [14] that the NVIDIA K40c, a GPU [16] could cope with.

Fig 5: UML Diagram for various steps for the proposed system

Assessing the proposed project:

The trained network produces a continuous numeral ranging from 0 to 1 representing Diabetic Retinopathy and other Diabetic Retinopathy groupings, analogous to the chance of the situation being present in the image. Diverging the operational threshold resulted in the plotting of receiver operating curves, and two operational points for the process were carefully chosen from the development set.

In order to compare the efficiency and validation of the algorithm set with 5 – 10 ophthalmologists, the primary operational point reflects the specificity of ophthalmologists to distinguish referable diabetic retinopathy (approximately 98%). The subsequent operational point corresponded to a compassion [9] of 97 percent for exposing diabetic retinopathy, which is a prerequisite in a hypothetical diagnosis tool.

Fig6: Flowchart of the proposed Diabetic Retinopathy Disease Detection algorithm.

Training the network: The CNN was initially trained on 10,290 images while waiting for it to achieve a meaningful level of accuracy. This was essential in order to accomplish a fairly swift classification [4] outcome without destroying sizable amount of training time. Following 120 times of training on the preliminary images [16], the network was trained for another 20 epochs on the full 78,000 training images [16]. Neural networks [13] deteriorate from acute over-fitting, notably in our dataset, where the majority of the images in the dataset are classified as exhibiting no indications of retinopathy. To address this matter, we improved by adding real-time class weights to the network.

The class-weights were modernized with a fraction proportional to how many images in the training set were classed as having no signs of Diabetic Retinopathy for each batch loaded for back - propagation. This greatly lowered the threat of over-fitting to a specific class. Stochastic gradient descent with Nesterov momentum was used to train the network. To stabilize the weights, a minimal learning rate of approximately 0.0001 was employed for 5 periods. This was but then risen to 0.0003 for the large 120 times of training on the early 10,290 images, increasing the model's exactitude to more than 60%, which got approximately 300+ hours of training. The network was later trained with a low learning rate on the entire training set of images. Within a few large epochs of the entire dataset, the network's correctness had expanded to 70 and more percentile. When training loss and accuracy reached a saturation point, the knowledge rate was dropped by a factor of ten.

Augmentation: The fundus images which were pre-processed earlier [3] were used for training the network. Following that, tangible data augmentation [16] was employed all the way through training to develop the network's skill to localise. Every single image was haphazardly augmented with arbitrary 0 - 90 degrees rotation, random true or no flat and straight up flips; and random flat and straight up shifts during each epoch.

In this assessment of retinal snapshots since grown-ups with diabetes, an algorithm founded on Deep Machine Learning had elevated compassion [9] and specificity for discovering ascribable Diabetic Retinopathy. Additional research is essential to clarify the feasibility of employing this algorithm in the medical regulation, as well as using the algorithm could have an advantage to better-quality care and endings when equated to contemporary ophthalmologic appraisal.

5. Implementation:

The prevalence of diabetes mellitus (inadequate production of insulin) is intensifying predominantly in low and intermediate - revenue nations and hitches owing to the syndrome are flattering chief wellbeing issues involving successful health intercessions for deterrence and medication. Diabetic Retinopathy is an imperative vascular impediment of diabetes that influences the sight of 2.6 million people worldwide and is responsible for 2.6 percent of global blindness (0.84 million of 32.4 million). To mitigate the impact of diabetic retinopathy, conditions for premature exposure, precise opinion, and timely treatment are needed.

A diabetes program's main goals are in establishing rules and benchmarks, in promoting surveillance, in encouraging prevention, in raising alertness, and in strengthening inhibition and control. The implementation of thorough programmes for the recognition and supervision of diabetic retinopathy has resulted in a reduction in the prevalence of this complication. The systematic and ocular pathophysiology of diabetic retinopathy extends beyond hyperglycaemia, Structure-function analyses show that diabetes affects the entire retina, leading to more sensitive and pathophysiology-based diagnosis, Combined ocular and systemic treatments have reduced the risk of vision loss in diabetics, and future steps will allow for personalised core are the key functions.

Method of Implementation:

To stipulate admittance to ocular attention to the low-revenue inhabitants with diabetes and to propose timely calculation and referral for appropriate treatment, to launch a health care network for the recommendation of patients with Diabetic Retinopathy for screening , assessment and Oscar verdict ,and treatment if obligatory ,to reinforce the methodological capability of medicinal crews affording acceptable guidance to expand the competence and excellence of Diabetic Retinopathy amenities are the ideas incorporated.

6. Testing:

To check whether the designed model is working or not

- a) Go to browser enter the URL <http://localhost:5000/>,
- b) Then the web page of our model will be displayed,
- c) Then select the button “Choose...” button. It direct to files where the dataset is saved,
- d) Select an image from either test or train folder,
- e) Image will be displayed on the web page,
- f) Then lastly, it will predict the retina image.

To reinforce the medical services, the proposed system will help the ophthalmologists improve the efficiency and quality of the diabetic retinopathy diagnosis. The detailed procedure of detecting whether an eye image is affected with Diabetic Retinopathy or not is explained pictorially. The step-by-step process will help in executing the detection and finally satisfies the proposed system.

The Fig 7 depicts the home web page of our proposed model, which prompts users to upload an eye image in order to predict whether or not the eye is affected by diabetic retinopathy. The images have already been collected and stored in the dataset. The new images can also be added to the dataset to aid in detection. To choose an image from the dataset click on “Choose” which directs the control to the dataset.

Fig 7: The web page of our proposed model “A Home page prompting to upload an Eye image”.

Fig 8: A prompt window for an Image to be chosen from the dataset.

When we click on “Choose...”, the control prompts us with a window to select an image from the dataset to test for the occurrence or non - occurrence of diabetic retinopathy in the selected eye image.

Fig 9: Uploaded an image from the dataset to test the symptoms of Diabetic Retinopathy.

The Fig 9 depicts the web page after selecting the required image from the dataset and the selected image is loaded on to the web page to test the symptoms of Diabetic Retinopathy. Once the persona is loaded on the web page click on “Click on this to see what it is!” to check the result of the selected image.

Fig 10: Predicting and Displaying the result after diagnosing the image.

After clicking on “Click on this to see what it is!” the result of the selected image is displayed as shown in Fig 10. The result of our proposed will be either No Diabetic Retinopathy disease detected, or Diabetic Retinopathy detected. Our proposed method will result in either No Diabetic Retinopathy disease detected (NO DRD), or Diabetic Retinopathy detected (DR).

Fig 11: Predicting and Displaying the result as Diabetic Retinopathy effected after diagnosing the image.

If the result of an image after diagnosing using our proposal is Diabetic Retinopathy Disease effected, the web page is displayed as shown in Fig 11. For validation purposes, 500 images from the dataset were saved. It took 100 seconds to run the images over the network. We define specificity for this 2-class [1] problem as the number of patients accurately labelled as having Diabetic Retinopathy out of the total accurate overall amount with the mentioned. We describe accuracy as the number of patients correctly classified. The final trained network achieved an accuracy of 75 – 80%. In the network, the classifications [4] were DRD and NO DRD.

The value of utilizing our trained CNN is that it can organize thousands of images each moment granting it to be operated in real – time whenever a new-found image is required. In practise, images are forwarded to clinicians for marking and not precisely graded when the patient arrives for testing. The trained CNN allows for a speedy diagnosis and instance answer to a patient. The network was also able to achieve these outcomes despite only having one image per eye.

Design of Test cases and Scenarios:

A test case is a series of actions that are executed to validate a precise feature or functionality of a software application. The prevailing Diabetic Retinopathy screening agenda is built on retinal photography, the performance of which is known to be reliant on the experience of the assessors’ and the techniques used. The implementation of supplementary screening tests might enhance performance, but it has significant financial repercussions. As part of the National Screening Programme for Diabetic Retinopathy’s battery of tests, colour[10] vision scanning could theoretically provide a cost-effective tool for diagnosing Diabetic Retinopathy.

Diabetic retinopathy affects nearly 80% of the Indian population. Diabetic retinopathy is an eye condition that affects diabetics who have high blood glucose (or sugar) levels for an extended period of time. The goal of this study is to detect diabetic retinopathy at an early stage by using a systematic approach that includes providing an input image, converting the image to grey [9] scale, and enhancing the images. Edge detection techniques are used to extract retinal features, and a match features template is used to detect abnormal retinal features. This technique aids in the accurate assessment of the severity of the proliferated disease.

7. Conclusion and Future Enhancements:

Despite the fact that the prevalence of Diabetic Retinopathy lingers to rise, the preceding era has witnessed the advent of innovative treatment opportunities, particularly VEGF-targeting treatments, which have deeply expanded our administration of DME and PDR endpoints. Nonetheless, there is a critical demand for effective fresh treatments for the entire stages of Diabetic Retinopathy, which emphasizes ongoing endeavours to entirely understand the convoluted approaches in which diabetes affects the retina. While considerable research effort has been guided towards distinguishing morbidic paths that contribute to the onset and evolution of Diabetic Retinopathy, a rising paradigm is the importance of endogenic mechanism that shield against Diabetic Retinopathy.

Quite a good considerable effort has been made to in identifying pathological residues in identifying and progression of diabetic retinopathy. It is noticed that nearly 50% of the patients from the dataset have diabetic retinopathy expected diabetics with long duration. Identification of such symptoms help in early detection of diabetic ocular, which helps in protection and prevention of diabetic retinopathy. Diabetic macular oedema, Glaucoma and Cataracts are few other types of diabetic retinopathy.

In upcoming scenario, accuracy can be calculated by applying convolution neural networks on the other data sets of diabetic retinopathies. A rigorous study of other machine learning algorithms can also be done to investigate the power of the model in predicting diabetic retinopathy images. We can conduct numerous experiments on larger data sets to reach the state of performance of the model. We can extend the proposal by developing mobile applications and can also integrate the proposal with Internet Of Things with decentralization concept having Edge Technology which accepts the input image dynamically, accessed anywhere from the world and reduces the computation time period over numerous images from the dataset.

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